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Policy Brief 2026/06
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Hikma v. Amarin decision: Supreme Court ruling on generic drug marketing liability

Issue/Problem

Since the [Hatch-Waxman Act](#), “[skinny labeling](#)” – through which a generic sells an FDA-approved product for indications outside of the brand manufacturer’s patent – has been used to allow generic drugs manufacturers to enter the market by carving out patented indications from their FDA-approved labels. Brand manufacturers have claimed induced infringement claims under [35 USC § 271\(b\)](#) to restrict generic from doing so, arguing that marketing of skinny-labelled drugs amounts to active encouragement to infringe patents.

Description of the Problem

Amarin Pharma developed and patented Vascepa, a drug for the treatment of severe hypertriglyceridemia. Hikma Pharmaceuticals, a generic manufacturer, introduced an FDA-approved equivalent to Vascepa by using a skinny label for indications outside of Amarin’s patents. Amarin nevertheless alleged that Hikma infringed on its patent because, in the totality of its communications, Hikma was inducing others to infringe their patent. On June 4, 2026, the Supreme Court of the United States held that this was not infringement.

Results

The Supreme Court reversed the US Court of Appeals for the Federal Circuit, holding that brand-name companies must prove “more than a sheer possibility” that generic manufacturers actively induced infringement. Under this standard, similar information in labels required by FDA requirements or regular marketing communications is not sufficient to prove inducement of infringement. However, the Supreme Court left open the possibility that more direct communications, such as those referencing patented materials or those sent directly to physicians, could constitute an induced infringement.

Lessons Learned

While Canadian courts have been dealing with skinny labels, they have [come to the opposite conclusion](#) from that in the US. One difference between the countries is that

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the US has specific legislation on skinny labels while Canada does not. This disparity could lead policymakers, concerned over high pharmaceutical prices, to consider similar legislation.